

Modern information and communication technologies and their use in foreign language teaching

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Abstract

It is known that knowledge of foreign languages is not only a cultural but also an economic need today. The need for rapid and effective mastery of communication with a foreign language has brought to life new forms and methods of teaching. One of the most effective forms of foreign language teaching is non-traditional forms of instruction based on role-playing games organized on television programs. It is very difficult to master communicative competence in English without the country of the language being translated. Therefore, the important task of the teacher is to create real and imaginary situations of communication in a foreign language lesson using different methods of work. It is important to acquaint students with the cultural values of the people - the mother tongue. Television shows are of great importance for this purpose.

Keywords: Foreign language, foreign language, information and communication technologies, television,

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Their use helps to realize the most important requirement of communicative methodology - to present the process of language learning as an understanding of the culture of living foreign languages; individualization of training and development and motivation of students' speech activity.

Another advantage of television shows is its emotional impact on students. The use of television programs also helps to develop various aspects of students' mental activity and primarily attention and memory.

During the game, organized on the basis of television programs, an atmosphere of joint learning activities is created in the classroom. In such a situation, even a careless student will be attentive. Thus, involuntary attention becomes voluntary, the intensity of which affects the process of memorization. The interest in television shows increases children's interest in English, which confirms their clear desire to be active participants in teacher-modeled conditioned speech situations, and to practice the learned phenomena of English in students' speech. to perform various grammatical exercises of the communicative direction to do.

Thus, the psychological features of the impact of television programs on students contribute to the strengthening of the learning process and create favorable conditions for the formation of students' communicative competence.

Role-playing games based on television shows help to engage the weaker learner in the learning process as well, as they demonstrate not only knowledge but also ingenuity and resourcefulness. In addition, a student who is weak in language teaching may be the first in the game: where ingenuity and resourcefulness sometimes turn out to be more important than knowing the topic.

A sense of equality, an atmosphere of enthusiasm and joy, an understanding that assignments can be completed - all of these allow students to use foreign words freely in speech and have a positive impact on learning outcomes.

It is these role-playing games that teach the norms of oral speech, ensuring the acquisition of the necessary communicative units in communication.

NUTQ KO'NIKMASI

It is in the context of the game that involuntary memorization takes place to a large extent. Role-playing classes are usually conducted in a lively, emotional, highly active, and comfortable psychological environment for students.

Games based on television programs have gained great popularity today due to their effectiveness. Using this form of foreign language teaching, the teacher can manage students' knowledge at any time without their knowledge, as parts of individual TV programs at all levels of learning can transfer students' knowledge and skills on a single topic and in a series. can be used as a form of covert control over topics.

The role-playing game helps to expand the scope of communication and conversation with foreign languages. This, in turn, involves pre-mastering the language material in the learning exercises and developing appropriate skills that allow students to focus on the content of the statement.

CHET TIL O'QITUVCHISINING KASBIY SIFATLARI

There is a simultaneous improvement and development of skills in the use of language materials in the role-playing game organized on the basis of television programs, but at this stage it is a peripheral task, the main thing is to communicate the situation and the role. Therefore, role-playing should be included in the final phase of the work on the topic.

It is difficult to overstate the importance of the media today: no area of our existence can be imagined without any information communication. Communication today takes place not only in society itself, as an interpersonal conversation, but also through the Internet, television, radio, newspapers, magazines and other means of communication. Today on the Internet you can not only find the information you need and read about the latest events, but also find something more useful for yourself, for example, the level of knowledge of English from your workplace You can take the test for.

In summary, the study seeks to shed light on the challenges associated with shaping students' positive motivational sphere. Today, electronic forms of media are becoming increasingly popular. It is online resources, portals and information services that are one of the most popular types of media today.

At the same time, the media has a significant impact on the formation of people's consciousness, so electronic and print media is an important part of the cultural and spiritual life of society. From these media sources, people gain knowledge that is always relevant and important to society.

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